

Polyrotaxane based leakage-proof and injectable phase change materials with high melting enthalpy and adjustable transition temperature

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Abstract

In this work, a series of advanced phase change materials (PCMs) were fabricated by using polyrotaxane (PLR) as supporter materials for encapsulating poly (ethylene glycol) (PEG). Phase-change enthalpy is mainly regulated by the PEG contents, whereas phase change temperature is controlled by PEG molecular weight. All PCMs have good form stabilities due to the good compatibility between PLR and PEG, and supporting ability of PLR. Given that the supporting material itself has phase-transition properties, the resulting composites have high phase change enthalpies (116.1-162.2 J g⁻¹) and very high enthalpy efficiency (>100%). It is a green and efficient preparation method because the whole preparation process did not involve organic solvents, and the material was prepared at room temperature. In addition, the obtained PCMs can be easily extruded and re-molded, which provides technical premise and convenience for the large-scale applications. As a typical application example, the PCMs showed its significant advantages in simulated solid-state drive model temperature

regulation, which fully demonstrates the practical and superior application value of the PCMs in the field of thermal management of electronic devices.

Keywords: phase change materials, thermal management, injectable, green pathway

ToC Figure

1. Introduction

To improve the efficiency of electronic devices thermal management, phase change materials (PCMs) attract lots of attention due to their high thermal energy storage capacity, adjustable working temperature range, and long-term stability.[1-3] However, the common issues of organic PCMs are their poor flexibility, and leakage during phase-change process. [4-6] To solve these problems, some porous support materials have usually been incorporated with organic PCM working substance to improve their form stability and realize solid-solid phase change. Generally, the traditional form stable PCMs use aerogel [2], microcapsules[7] and some other polymers (with high melting point [8] but no phase change effect when reaching the PCM substance melting temperature) to support the structure of the PCMs. [9] In order to prevent the leakage of PCMs, these composites often use materials without phase change ability as support materials. Therefore, while obtaining form stability, the PCMs also lose energy storage capacity. There are two reasons for the losing of thermal storage capacity: (1) the energy storage capacity of the composite is reduced by the support material without phase change ability; (2) the PCM is bound by the support material in a narrow space, and some of the chain segments cannot crystallize and melt normally and efficiently, which further reduces the energy storage capacity of the PCMs. Therefore, the enthalpy efficiency of conventional PCM is usually lower than 100%. We think that the supporter materials with typical phase transition behavior and suitable phase transition temperature should be selected as one of the effective ways to solve the problem of enthalpy capacity losing.

In addition, the PCMs prepared by traditional methods also have some typical deficiencies. For example, PCMs prepared by microcapsule method usually have relatively low dimension and is necessary to be further encapsulated for practical application. Furthermore, the enthalpy of phase transition may decrease greatly [10]. Conventional polymer based PCM also faces common challenges, such as low encapsulation efficiency, low enthalpy and consuming of organic solvents. [11] Most of the conventional methods are difficult to achieve convenient and repeatable processing. Especially, the 3D porous materials loaded PCM is usually difficult to achieve flexibility and re-molding. [12-14] These shortcomings limit their wide application, because the

realization of repeated processing or plastic processing of PCM can facilitate the mass-production for the wide application.

The PCMs thermal regulation market on the mobile phone, computer and other mobile terminals is in full bloom under 5G era. The application of renewable materials is currently considered as a necessity for sustainable development. [15, 16] Therefore, developing ecofriendly energy management materials is vital for sustainable research.[17]

Polyethylene glycol (PEG)-based PCMs are widely used as PCM work substance in the fields of solar energy harvesting and waste heat recovery. [18] The supporter materials with typical phase transition behavior in the shape-stabilized PCMs have been reported. For example, polymeric solid-solid PCMs were used as the supporting materials of shape-stabilized PCMs in some literatures: Novel form stable phase change materials based on the composites of polyethylene glycol/polymeric solid-solid phase change material.[19] Form-stable phase change materials with high phase change enthalpy from the composite of paraffin and cross-linking phase change structure. [20] Binary shape-stabilized phase change materials based on poly(ethylene glycol)/polyurethane composite with dual-phase transition.[21] Polyrotaxane (PLR) has good processability and high shape stability. [22] Integrating the typical disadvantages of traditional PCM and the requirements of PCM advanced processing and green manufacturing, in this work, we will choose the high flexible PLR as the support materials, because the molecular chain of PLR is almost the same as PEG, and PLR itself is also a PCM with excellent performance, especially the form stability. We believe that it will be an ideal support material for PEG based PCMs. So as to ensure that the final PCMs have the following advantages: (1) good durability, high enthalpy efficiency after melting and cooling process, (2) indicating excellent leakage proof performance, and (3) green and convenient processability and reprocess ability, which provides practical basis for the wide application of the corresponding PCMs.

2. Results and discussion

2.1. Preparation, form stability and mechanical performance of PCM

Figure 1a shows the preparation two-step process of the PCMs. The synthesis of PLR as the step 1 is reported in previous work. [22] The structure of PLR can be confirmed by ^1H nuclear magnetic

resonance, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy and solubility (**Figure S1-S3**). For the step 2, the PEG solution (including PEG1k, PEG1.5k or PEG 6K) was directly mixed and stirred with the newly prepared PLR solution. The specific component contents are shown in **Table S1**. The selected proportions of PLR/PEG6k PCM are 30 wt%, 60 wt%, 90 wt%, 120 wt%, 150 wt%, 200 wt%, 250 wt%, 300 wt% and 350 wt%, in order to regulate the phase change enthalpy. The obtained sample sheets with different thickness can be realized by hot pressing. **Figure 1b** shows the XRD curve of sample PPEG6-150. The XRD curves of other samples are all provide in **Figure S4-5**. As it can be seen, PEG shows two peaks at 19.2° and 23.3° , which are attributed to crystal planes (120) and concerted (112)/(032) planes, respectively. [23] In addition, the characteristic peaks at $2\theta = 5.37^\circ$, 7.44° , 10.84° , and 12.10° were observed (Figure 1b). The values are almost the same as those reported in a past report: 5.30° (001), 7.41° (100), 10.9° (002), and 12.8° (110) obtained from the dried PLR crystal consisting of α -Cyclodextrin (α -CD) and PEO, [24] which is termed as α -CD crystal unit (in this work) as shown in Figure 1a (see the blue rectangle shape). These α -CD crystal units may well maintain in a certain temperature range, so as to act as a physical cross-linking point. The microstructure is further shown in **Figure 1c** and **Figure 1d**. During the phase transformation, the free segments of PEO or PEG melt and crystallize, and the shape stability of PCM is guaranteed by the α -CD crystal units or entanglement of PEO molecular chains. The photos of pure PEG and PLR/PEG using hot plate treatment at different temperature are shown in **Figure 1e-f**. PEG fully melted at 70°C in 1 hour, but all the PLR/PEG PCMs showed no significant appearance changes. There is no leakage and shape change during the heating, which indicates that the PLR/PEG PCMs have good form stability. (**Figure S6**)

It was found that the PPEG0.6-150, PPEG0.6-40 and PPEG0.4-150 showed significant leakage, as shown in **Figure S7**. Since PEG1k and PEG1.5k have no leakage at 70°C for a long time (Figure 1f), we can assign that increasing the molecular weight is conducive to avoid PEG substance leakage. Therefore, it is suggested that the molecular weight of PEG should be higher than that of PEG1k ($M_n=1304\text{ g mol}^{-1}$, $PDI=1.04$) in current material system.

We have carried out tensile mechanical tests on the series of PPEG6k samples. The key parameters are all presented in **Figure 1g** and **Figure 1h**. Detailed mechanical data are listed in

Table S2. Concretely, as shown in Figure 1g, with the increase of PEG 6k content, Young's modulus increased, while tensile strength and elongation% decreased. We choose 150% as the load ratio for analyzing the influence of molecular weight on mechanical performance. As shown in Figure 1h, the molecular weight of PEG increased, Young's modulus and tensile strength were significantly increased, and elongation at break decreased. The changes of these mechanical properties are affected by the aggregation morphology of PCM such as molecular weight and molecular crystallization.

Furthermore, we cut the sample to 50 mm×40 mm×0.5 mm, and the flexibility was tested simply by bending with two fingers. As shown in **Figure 1g**, the elongation decreases with the increase of PEG6k (from 30 wt% to 350 wt%). When the content of PEG is higher than 300 wt%, the material can hardly be bent (but the material still has good leakage resistance and mechanical support, see Section 2.5 and the related sample PPEG6-350). Sample PPEG1-150 and PPEG1.5-150 are endowed with ultra-high flexibility due to their low T_m (see **Figure 1i, 1j** and **Figure S8**). The bending images of other samples are shown in **Figure S9**.

Figure 1. (a) PCM preparation routes: step 1, synthesis of PLR and step 2, encapsulation of PEG, (b) XRD curve of typical sample PPEG6-150, (c) diagram of melting state of the PCM, (d) diagram of crystallization state of the material at room temperature, (e) schematic diagram of form stability test for representative samples: PEG6k, PPEG6-150, PPEG6-250 and PPEG6-350, (f) form stability test of the samples: PEG 1k, PEG 1.5k, PPEG1-150 and PPEG1.5-150, (g) mechanical properties of sample PPEG6-30, PPEG6-60, PPEG6-90, PPEG6-120, PPEG6-150 and PPEG6-200, (h) mechanical properties of sample PPEG1-150, PPEG1.5-150 and PPEG6-150, and flexible schematic diagram of PPEG1-150 sheet (thickness ~ 0.5 mm) with (i) folded shape and (j) curled shape.

2.2. Phase change process of the PCM

We observed the crystal morphology of typical samples by polarized optical microscopy. **Figures 2a-c** correspond to the spherulite morphologies of PPEG6-150, PPEG1.5-150 and PPEG1-150, respectively. A typical spherocrystal pattern was observed for all the three selected samples. The particle size distribution for sample PPEG6-150 is shown in Figure 2a inset, with an average particle size of ~ 220 μm and unimodal distribution. A spherocrystal pattern similar to that for PPEG6-150 was also observed for sample PPEG1.5-150 (**Figure 2b**), however, the spherocrystal size were much smaller than those of the PPEG6-150. In addition, the spherulite size shows a relatively continuous bimodal distribution (peak 1 at 155 μm and peak 2 at 80 μm). No homogeneous spherocrystal patterns were observed for sample PPEG1-150. In **Figure 2c**, large spherulites (~160 μm) and very small spherulites coexist. Due to the limitation of software and image definition, the particle size distribution in small size range cannot be given reasonably (Figure 2c inset). The Gibbs-Thomson equation [25] predicts that the melting point depression melting temperature (T_m) for a crystal of size d_c [m] is given by the following equation:

$$T_m = T_m^0 - \frac{2\sigma T_m^0}{d_c \rho_c \Delta H^0} \quad (1)$$

where, σ [J m^{-2}] is the surface energy of the interface, T_m^0 is the equilibrium melting temperature, T_m [$^{\circ}\text{C}$] is the melting point of crystals of size d , ΔH^0 [J g^{-1}] is the bulk enthalpy of fusion, and ρ_c [kg m^{-3}] is the density of the solid. According to equation (1), the smaller crystal size has lower melting

point. Therefore, the size and distribution of the grains in Figure 2a-c directly determine the DSC scanning curve of the samples (**Figure 2d**). In sample PPEG6-150, PEG6k and PLR can form spherulites with relative uniform size, and thus show a significant single peak distribution (in both crystallization and melting process). The other two samples show bimodal melting behaviors. This is mainly due to the significant crystal size and distribution differences. DSC data of other samples are shown in **Figure S10-S21**. The crystallinity data are listed in **Table S3**. It can be found that the crystallinity of the samples generally remains at a high level of $> 75\%$, which is also the practical premise to ensure that high enthalpy of PCM.

Figure 2. POM image, crystal size and distribution of (a) PPEG6-150, (b) PPEG1.5-150, (c) PPEG1-150, (d) DSC curves of sample PPEG6-150, PPEG1.5-150 and PPEG1-150, (e) melting status of PPEG6-150 (top), PPEG1.5-150 and PPEG1-150 (bottom), (f) Crystal status of PPEG6-150 (top), PPEG1.5-150 and PPEG1-150 (bottom), (g) melting temperature ($T_{m,p}$) of sample PLR, PEG 6k, and

PPEG6-150, (h) melting temperature of samples PLR, PPEG1.5-150 (two peaks) and PEG 1.5k, and (i) melting temperature of samples PLR ($T_m=64.40$ °C [20]), PPEG1-150 (two peaks) and PEG 1k.

Based on the above experimental results, we can interpret the phase transition process of this series of phase change materials in detail. When the temperature is below the melting temperature of α -CD crystal units, the α -CD crystal unit will maintain. According to the previous reports, the melting point of α -CD crystal unit is 98.32°C. [22] Therefore, the shape of the material can be well maintained at 70 °C (the form stability test temperature) in this study. In other words, the α -CD crystal unit will be stable at the melting temperature of PEG or PEO. During the heating process, PEG molecules form random molecular chains, and PEG does not leak due to the restriction of PLR frameworks (Figure 1e and 1f) during the heating process. Concretely, as shown in **Figure 2e, 2f** (in sample PPEG6-150), the crystallization of PEG and PLR was almost synchronous to form relatively large and uniform spherulites. For the PPEG1-150 and PPEG1.5-150, because of its low crystallization temperature, it is necessary to start crystallization when the PLR crystallization reaches a certain degree. The delayed crystallization of PEG will complete crystallization in the confined space. PLR was also affected by the impurities of low molecular PEG in the crystallization process, and when PEG began to crystallize, there was a competitive relationship between PLR and PEG crystallization. As a result, the melting points of both PLR and PEG in PLR were significantly lower than those of pristine PLR and pure PEG, respectively, as shown in **Figure 2g-i** and the following formulas, $T_{m,PEG6k} < T_{m1} = T_{m2} < T_{m,PLR}$ (for sample PPEG6-150), and $T_{m1} < T_{m,PLR}$, and $T_{m2} < T_{m,PEG}$ (for both sample PPEG1.5-150 and PPEG1-150), where T_{m1} , T_{m2} are the melting temperature of PLR and PEG in PCMs (as shown in Figure 2d), respectively, and $T_{m,PLR}$, $T_{m,PEG}$ are the peak melting temperature of pristine PLR (64.40 °C) and the temperature of pure PEG (PEG 6k, PEG 1.5k and PEG 1k), respectively.

Table 1. Some PCMs parameters.

Samples	Melting Enthalpy (J g ⁻¹)		Real enthalpy efficiency (EEr, %)	Extent of supercooling (°C)	Melting point (T _{peak} , °C)	Crystallinity (%)	Leakage
	Measured	Calculated ΔH_m					

	ΔH_m						
PEG 1k	166.4	-	-	8.7	38.5	84.7	Yes
PEG 1.5k	167.4	-	-	5.7	49.5	85.2	Yes
PEG 6k	176.2	-	-	22.5	58.5	89.7	Yes
PPEG6-30	116.1	95.5	130.7	7.4	66.3	79.5	No
PPEG6-60	123.7	110.6	122.1	7.9	61.2	79.6	No
PPEG6-90	126.8	121.0	114.6	9.5	62.4	78.3	No
PPEG6-120	127.8	128.5	108.4	8.9	62.2	76.7	No
PPEG6-150	133.9	134.2	108.2	9.2	61.8	78.7	No
PPEG6-200	140.1	141.2	106.7	11.1	63.9	80.2	No
PPEG6-250	151.2	146.2	110.5	9.9	64.7	85.1	No
PPEG6-300	158.7	150.0	112.4	9.7	61.0	88.2	No
PPEG6-350	162.2	152.9	112.1	9.1	63.1	90.8	No
PPEG1.5-150	133.4	128.4	107.8	-13.6	46.5, 54.0	78.4	No
PPEG1-150	129.8	129.0	104.9	-7.7	34.5, 56.8	76.2	No

Note: the extent of supercooling and crystallinity were both calculated according to the second heating and second cooling in DSC results. $\Delta H_{m,calcd.} = \omega_{PEG}\Delta H_{PEG} + \omega_{PLR}\Delta H_{PLR}$, where ω_{PEG} is the weight percentage of PEG, ΔH_{PEG} is the enthalpy of PEG, ω_{PLR} is the weight percentage of PLR, and ΔH_{PLR} is the enthalpy of PLR, with value of 71.3 J g^{-1} . [22]

2.3. PCM performance

2.3.1. Thermal storage and cycling performance

Figure 3. (a) Enthalpy results of all PEG 6k related samples, (b) melting temperature (T_m that is obtained from DSC curve) of samples PPEG1-150, PPEG1.5-150 and PPEG6-150, (c) enthalpy efficiency (both EER and EEc), (d) the measured and calculated values of enthalpy, (e) extent of supercooling of all the PCM samples, (f) the cycle performance of PPEG6-150 as a typical example. The cycle performance of some other samples (PPEG6-90 and PPEG6-350) is shown in **Figure S22**. Comparison for (g) latent heat and (h) enthalpy efficiency to the reports elsewhere.

We can control the latent heat of phase transition by adding different amounts of PEG. As shown in **Figure 3a**, the enthalpy increases with the increase of PEG6k contents. The phase transition enthalpy of sample PPEG6-350 can be as high as 162.2 J g^{-1} when the addition amount reaches 350% ($w_{\text{PEG}}=77.8 \text{ wt.}\%$). We can also adjust the phase transition temperature of PCM by changing the molecular weight of PEG. As shown in **Figure 3b**, by adding PEG1k, PEG1.5k or PEG6k, the peak temperature of phase transition can be regulated from $\sim 30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $\sim 60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Furthermore, the conventional enthalpy efficiency (EEc) of PCMs (PEG) can be determined by equation (2), [26, 27]

$$EEc \% = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\omega \Delta H_{PCM}} \times 100 \% \quad (2)$$

where, ΔH_m [J g⁻¹] is the enthalpy value of the target PCMs. ΔH_{PCM} [J g⁻¹] represents the enthalpy of PCM substance, namely, PEG, and ω [%] is the mass ratio of PEG in the PCMs. While the real enthalpy efficiency (EEr) of the PCM can be determined by equation (3),

$$EEr \% = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\omega \Delta H_{m,PCM} + (1-\omega) \Delta H_{m,Supporter}} \times 100 \% \quad (3)$$

where, ω [%] is the weight content of PEG, ΔH_{PCM} [J g⁻¹] is the enthalpy of PEG, and $\Delta H_{Supporter}$ [J g⁻¹] is the melting enthalpy of PLR. In the conventional case, the supporter does not contribute to the enthalpy, that is to say $\Delta H_{Supporter} = 0$. Therefore, $EEc \% = EEr \%$. However, PLR plays a dual role in this research, namely, both supporter and PCM substance, thus, $EEc \% > EEr \%$ (**Figure 3c**).

The heat losses and ΔH_s were calculated and listed in **Table S3**. The PCMs exhibited a high enthalpies (116.1~162.2 J g⁻¹, **Figure 3a**) and high enthalpy efficiency. In addition, the specific calculation formula for calculated enthalpy ($\Delta H_{m,Cacld.}$) is as follows,

$$\Delta H_{m,Cacld.} = \Delta H_{m,PLR} + \omega(\Delta H_{m,PEG} - \Delta H_{m,PLR}) \quad (4)$$

where, $\Delta H_{m,PEG}$ [J g⁻¹] and $\Delta H_{m,PLR}$ [J g⁻¹] are the enthalpy of PEG and PLR, respectively, and ω [%] is the weight percentage of PEG in the target PCMs. It is found that the calculated value of phase transition enthalpy is in good agreement with the measured value when PEG is with certain region (from ~40 wt% to ~80 wt%) (**Figure 3d**), which indicates the solidification of PLR and PEG is relative independent within these compositions. The corresponding data are listed in Table 1 and shown in Figure 3d. The extent of supercooling (ΔT , °C) was calculated by equation (5):

$$\Delta T = T_{m,onset} - T_{s,onset} \quad (5)$$

where, $T_{m,onset}$ [°C] is onset temperature of melting and $T_{s,onset}$ [°C] is onset temperature of solidification. Based on equation (5), ΔT of the PCMs encapsulating PEG 6k are all calculated to be ~10 °C (**Table 1**). As shown in **Figure 3e**, negative superercooling occurs for both sample PPEG1-150 and PPEG1.5-150. The negative value is calculated according to the definition formula (5). Because the macro spherulite component of the material melts later and crystallizes first. In this way, there is a significant overlap temperature zone between the crystallization process and the melting

range, so the negative index can be obtained based on equation (5). This shows that the supercooling can be eliminated by blending PEG with different molecular weight on the basis of the definition formula (5).

Figure 3f shows the cycle curves of the typical sample PPEG6-150. After 40 cycles, the material still shows a very stable cooling and heating process (**Figure S23**). The PCMs sheets had high cycle performance because the main parameters (ΔH_m , ΔH_s and melting temperature values were listed on Figure S23) remained almost unchanged after 40 cycles.

2.3.2 Comparison with the important indicators in the literature

Table 2. Methods and properties comparison about PEG or PEO based PCMs.

Composition	Methods	Solvents	ΔH_m (J g ⁻¹)	Enthalpy efficiency (%)	Reference
PEG/Halloysite nanotube	Melt-extrusion	-	96.80-115.90	>95.16	[28]
PEO/CNC	Solution mixing	H ₂ O	66.00–93.00	-	[29]
PEG/cellulose acetate/TDI	Electrospinning +crosslinking	Toluene, Acetone and N, N-dimethylacetamide	36.72-86.03	-	[30]
PEG/ PVA/Graphene aerogel	Sol-gel/hydrothermal reaction	H ₂ O	119.60-145.80	-	[31]
PEG/ β -CD/MDI	Crosslinking copolymers	N, N-dimethylformamide	90.34-111.60	69.02-88.01	[32]
PEG/IPDI/f-PDAPs	Crosslinking	Methyl ethyl ketone	71.10-72.20	-	[33]
PEG/Xylitol/4, diphenylmethane diisocyanate	4'- Crosslinking copolymers	-	68.40-80.46	-	[34]
Halloysite nanotubes/PEG/HDIB	Crosslinking copolymers	N, N-dimethylformamide	83.80-123.70	76.60-82.90	[35]
Graphene oxide/PEG/ HDIB	Crosslinking copolymers	N, N-dimethylformamide	71.70-78.00	52.47-57.32	[36]
PEG/IPDI/phloroglucinol	Crosslinking (PU)	Methyl ethyl ketone	117.10-146.60	-	[37]
PEG/glucose/4, diphenylmethane diisocyanate	4'- Crosslinking (PU)	N, N-dimethylformamide	108.70-131.90	-	[19]
PEG/4, 4'-diphenylmethane	Crosslinking (PU)	-	76.63-	57.05-71.67	[38]

diisocyanate /castor oil					117.70	
PEG/Ethylene glycol	Hydrogel		H ₂ O		~100.00- 150.00	- [39]
PEG/CNT@Cr-MIL-101-NH ₂	Physical blending and impregnating		Ethanol		83.10- 124.90	- [40]
PU/CNT (PEG+HDI for PCM)	Solution assisted infiltration		N, dimethylformamide	N-	119.38- 132.02	- [41]
PEG+HDI+PNF	Linear PU		N-methyl-2- pyrrolidone		145.00- 150.63	83.33-88.34 [42]
PEG+TDI+Melamine	Crosslinking		N, dimethylformamide	N-	78.20- 118.70	- [43]
PEO/ α -CD	Host-guest recognition		H ₂ O		57.11- 104.29	92.79-99.87 [22]
PEO/ α -CD/PEG	Blending		H ₂ O		116.10- 162.20	(104.90- 130.70)/(133.90- 395.30) This work

Note: Cellulose nano crystal=CNC; Toluene diisocyanate=TDI; Polyvinyl alcohol=PVA; 4,4'-diphenylmethane diisocyanate=MDI; Hexamethylene Diisocyanate Biuret=HDIB; Phosphorylated polyvinyl alcohol=PPVA; f-PDAPs ^[32] = furan-modified polydopamine particles; Isophorone diisocyanate=IPDI; Carbon nanotube=CNT and PNF is phosphorene nanoflakes.

We made a comparison for the preparation method, melting enthalpy, *etc.* reported in the literature elsewhere to highlight the advantages of both PCM preparation method and enhanced phase transition performance (**Table 2**, **Figure 3g** and **Figure 3h**). Conventionally, PEG-based PCMs are usually fabricated by solvent casting, chemical crosslinking, and porous materials encapsulation. Notably, one of the typical advantages of the current study is the green and convenient preparation process. Moreover, as shown in Figure 3g-h, both the enthalpies and the enthalpy efficiency are with the highest level as the reported in some recent works. All the above results support that the materials reported in current work have significant advantages in both preparation pathways and melting enthalpies. Notably, compared with the leakage proof PCM obtained by traditional chemical methods, this work will not involve the use of organic solvents. Moreover, biomass cyclodextrin is used, which improves the sustainability of the PCMs to a certain extent.

2.4. Heat response and process ability

Figure 4a is the thermal response images of samples PPEG1-150, PPEG1.5-150, PPEG6-150, PPEG6-250 and PPEG6-350 on the hot plate at 85 °C. The specific temperature vs. time curves are shown in **Figure 4b** and **Figure 4c**. As it can be seen in Figure 4b, PPEG1-150 presents two phase transition platforms of A1 (< 40 °C) and A2 (< 60 °C). In the curve of PPEG1.5-150, the B1 and B2 platforms are quite close. For sample PPEG6-150, the material maintains a relatively stable temperature for a long time from ~60 °C. The temperature rise of the PPEG6-150 sample is faster than that of the other two samples in the first 20 s because there is no phase transition for sample PPEG6-150 at the beginning. As soon as the plateau region passes, the sample continues to rise to the equilibrium temperature. Due to the delay of phase transition for a long time, the time to reach the equilibrium temperature for sample PPEG6-150 will lag behind the other two samples. Figure 4c shows the temperature increasing curve of PPEG6-150, PPEG6-250 and PPEG6-350. In the initial stage, the heating rate is almost the same. The time for the three samples to enter the platform is quite similar. It can be further found that the phase change period increased with the increasing of PEG6k contents. This is because the higher latent heat, the longer the thermal control time under the condition of equal size, same heat source and similar thermal conductivity (the thermal conductivity of sample PPEG1-150, PPEG6-150 and PPEG6-250 are 0.31 ± 0.02 W/(m·K), 0.30 ± 0.05 W/(m·K) and 0.33 ± 0.03 W/(m·K), respectively). Specifically, there is a good linear relationship between the phase transition period (s) and the enthalpy (**Figure 4d**), as described by the following equation (6):

$$\text{Phase change period} = 1.86\Delta H_m - 208.70, R^2 = 0.999 \quad (6)$$

where, phase change period is the time in the heating curves of PCM from beginning to the ending of phase change (Figure 4c), and ΔH_m is the enthalpy of the PCM obtained by DSC test.

In addition, we found that the samples have thermoplastic properties. PPEG1-150 was selected as a typical representative to show the processing possibility and convenience of phase change materials. As shown in **Figure 4e-h**, the sample is injectable, knittable, pelletizable and re-

moldable. That is to say we can easily make filaments or pellets, which provides a convenient possibility for PCM to realize 3D printing.

Figure 4i shows the elastic modulus G' and viscous modulus G'' vs. strain of PPEG1-150, PPEG1.5-150 and PPEG6-150 at 80 °C. As seen in Figure 4i, all the three samples show linear viscoelastic behavior at strain from 0.05~4 % under a frequency of 10 rad s⁻¹ at 80 °C. **Figure 4j** demonstrates the rheological data (G' and G'' vs. frequency) of the three PCMs with different PEG molecular weights at 80 °C. We found that both G' and G'' were independent upon the frequencies, and G' was higher than G'' at all presented frequencies for all the three samples. This result confirms that these samples can be considered as gels^[31]. The gel formation could be the result of the formation of PEO entanglement and α -CD crystal units. As seen in Figure 4 j, G' increased as the PEG molecule weight increased, indicating the stiffness of the samples increased when the PEG molecule weight increased. In addition, the crossover of G' and G'' were observed for all the three PCMs in the specific frequency region. Before the crossover, the PCM behaviors as viscous fluid. After the crossover, namely $\omega > 0.1$ rad s⁻¹ for PPEG6-150, $\omega > 0.5$ rad s⁻¹ for PPEG1.5-150 and $\omega > 10$ rad s⁻¹ for PPEG1-150 (point A, B and C in Figure 4j), all the three PCMs behavior as elastic solid. **Figure 4k** shows the rheological data of PPEG6-150, PPEG1.5-150 and PPEG1-150 samples (2 °C min⁻¹). The samples started to be soft after T_f , resulting in the jumping rheological data. The viscous flow temperature (T_f) was defined as the onset temperature at which G' changed greatly during heating accordingly. The samples exhibited liquid states after T_f . As seen, the T_f values ranged from 95.4 to 124.1 °C, which are much higher than the melting temperature of PEG. Furthermore, it was found that the T_f value obviously increased with increasing the PEG molecular weight. We can assign that T_f is the minimum temperature for easy processing of materials. Because T_f (PPEG1-150) is 95.4 °C, this is the direct basis for us to select 100 °C as the processing temperature of melt micro mixing extrusion of PPEG1-150 sample.

2.5. Application of the PCM

A typical application of phase change materials is the thermal management of electronic devices. As shown in **Figure 5a**, phase change materials usually work with metal heatsink to regulate the temperature of solid state disk (SSD). In order to meet the needs of convenient laboratory testing, we

designed a schematic structure (semi-SSD based device, **Figure 5b**). As shown in Figure 5b, the metal sheets (Copper sheet, 1 mm in thickness), protecting sheet (Polypropylene (PP) with 2 mm in thickness), PCM (70 mm×22 mm×1 mm in thickness, which is the same as the size of commercial product) and the top metal heatsink stacked together from the bottom to the top. **Figure 5c** shows the schematic diagram of the whole material test system. **Figure 5d** is a top view photograph of two schematic devices with PCM (following the stacking structure shown in Figure 5b). The specific images of PCM samples (both commercial one and sample PPEG6-350) with the calculated thermal absorption capacities is shown in **Figure S24**. **Figure 5e** shows the IR images of different samples at different heating time. We can further obtain the measured temperature change heating curves, as shown in **Figure 5f**.

Figure 5. (a) Real application form of the PCM for SSD thermal management, (b) illustration of the experimental stack structure of the device, (c) test process and sample test diagram: including sample heating, signal acquisition and data storage, (d) the structure diagram of the designed device, (e) IR

images of the devices during heating at 85 °C, (f) the heating curves of the devices that without PCM, with commercial PCM sample, and with PPEG6-350, and (g) the general heating curves illustration of the devices that with commercial sample, and PCM with high enthalpy.

As shown in Figure 5f and **Figure 5g**, the endothermic and exothermic state of the analog device can form a relatively stable equilibrium state at last. During the whole heating cycle, sample PPEG6-350 in this study showed significantly better temperature control state than both the blank samples and commodities. Specifically, the temperature of the protecting part with PCM was significantly lower than that of blank sample and commercial PCM. Furthermore, there was no significant difference in the initial stage (I, linear heating stage, Figure 5g). When entering the phase transition region (region II), the temperature difference gradually appears and maintain between 5 and 6 °C for ~30 min. The difference is due to the high enthalpy effect of PPEG6-350 phase transition, which plays a role in temperature regulation for a long time. When the phase transformation reaches the capacity, that is, PCM melts totally, the heat absorption of the material will be absorbed in the form of sensible heat, which will increase the temperature and approach the equilibrium temperature finally. This is also the reason why in Figure 5f and 5g, the temperature of the third stage (III) is close to the commodity or blank sample. The DSC curve of the commercial PCM is given in **Figure S25**. It can be found that the latent heat of PCM is very small. Therefore, the thermal control mainly depends on its heat conduction to the soaking plate to achieve heat dissipation. In this study, the significant existence of temperature difference for a long time fully proves the significant utility of PCM. At the same time, it also shows the practical significance of PCM in the field of thermal control of electronic devices. We expect that under the premise of maintaining high latent heat, and then further improve the thermal conductivity of the material, it is expected that more significant heat management effect will be achieved. The corresponding work will continue to be reported in the near future.

3. Conclusion

In this work, we realized supramolecular PLR as the support material to encapsulate different molecular weight and different content of PEG to prepare high performance phase change materials.

The α -CD crystal units can keep the shape during melting of PEG and act as the physical crosslinking point. The structural similarity between PLR and PEG ensures the compatibility between PLR and PEG, so there is no leakage of PEG ($M_n > 1304 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$) during the phase transition. PLR/PEG PCMs can ensure the shape stability within PEG contents of 30 wt.% - 350 wt.%. In addition, by introducing PEG with different molecular weight, the phase transition temperature can be adjustable from 30 °C to 60 °C. The enthalpy of phase transition can be adjustable from 116.1 to 162.2 J g⁻¹. Because the molecular chains promote each other and the support material itself is also a phase change material, the enthalpy efficiency is significantly higher than 100%. For sample PPEG1-150 and PPEG1.5-150, the supercooling was calculated as -13.62 °C and -7.66 °C, respectively. These materials can be used as thermal control sheets for electronic devices such as SSD. Compared with commercial PCM, the PPEG6-350 has better temperature control effect (There is usually a temperature difference of more than 5 °C) on the heating device in a certain time range. This work provides a basis for the development of simple, efficient, green and high-performance PEG based phase change materials. Moreover, the excellent process ability has laid a solid foundation for its industrial application.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Guang-Zhong Yin: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Writing-original draft, Writing-review & editing. **Alba Marta López:** Data curation, Methodology, Writing-review & editing. **Xiao-Mei Yang:** Data curation, Writing-review & editing. **Xiang Ao:** Data curation, Writing-review & editing. **Jose Hobson:** Data curation, Writing-review & editing. **De-Yi Wang:** Methodology, Writing-review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

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